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1 Midterm Review Success

1 In June 2025, the RESCALE project underwent its official midterm review with the European Commission. The review confirmed that the project has **fully achieved its objectives and milestones for the first reporting period (M1-M18)**. Reviewers **1** highlighted the consortium’s strong progress in developing the **RESCALE toolbox**, including the Trusted Bill of Materials (TBOM), advanced static and dynamic analysis tools, and the first integrated **MVP validated in pilots**. **2**

The project was praised for its **high-quality scientific contributions**, with 14 peer-reviewed publications already delivered, as well as for launching **credible pilot environments** that demonstrated the platform’s capabilities. The overall execution was assessed as very well implemented and on track, with RESCALE positioned to make a significant impact on European supply chain security in the coming period.

Minimum Viable Product (MVP)

The RESCALE consortium has already delivered the first integrated MVP of the platform. The MVP brings together core components such as the **TBOM**, advanced **static and dynamic analysis modules**, and the **Trust Orchestrator** framework. It has been successfully deployed and validated in pilot environments, providing early evidence of technical integration and readiness. This milestone demonstrates that RESCALE is well on track to deliver innovative solutions for supply chain security.

Meetings

In the 2nd year of the project, RESCALE organized the following project meetings:

- 3rd Plenary Meeting, Amsterdam, hosted by VUA
- 4th Plenary Meeting, Braunschweig, hosted by AEGIS
- S&T meetings, hosted by AEGIS
- Consortium meetings

Deliverables

A total of **15** deliverables were submitted in the 2nd year of the project:

- D1.3 – Period 1 Project Report
- D2.2 – Use Case Specification (final version)
- D2.4 – Technology Analysis and Requirements Specification (final version)
- D2.6 – High Level Architecture (final version)
- D3.1 – Static Code Analysers and Formal Verification Methods (first version)
- D3.3 – Dynamic Testing Analysis Components (first version)
- D3.5 – Hardware Vulnerability and Leakage Detection (first version)
- D3.7 – Solutions for Security Testing of Low-Level System Components (first version)
- D4.2 – RESCALE Continuous Security Assurance Platform (first version)
- D4.4 – TBOM Security and Trust Mechanism (first version)
- D5.1 – Trust Orchestrator (first version)
- D5.3 – Pilot Deployment, Test and Demonstration (first version)
- D5.5 – Validation and Evaluation Report (first version)
- D6.2 – Dissemination Report (first version)
- D6.4 – Initial Exploitation Plan

Publications

X total publications have been submitted by RESCALE partners in the 1st/2nd/3rd year. An indicative list follows:

- Safeguarding Blockchain and DLTs From Arbitrary and Malicious Content. [Not uploaded](#)
- Game On: A Performance Comparison of Interpolation Techniques Applied into Shamir's Secret Sharing. <https://zenodo.org/records/14257578>
- hwdbg: Debugging Hardware Like Software. <https://zenodo.org/records/17009872>
- Half Spectre, Full Exploit: Hardening Rowhammer Attacks with Half Spectre Gadgets. [Not uploaded](#)
- Training Solo: On the Limitations of Domain Isolation Against Spectre-v2 Attacks. [Not uploaded](#)
- LibAFLGo: Evaluating and Advancing Directed Greybox Fuzzing. [Not Uploaded](#)
- Phantom Trails: Practical Pre-Silicon Discovery of Transient Data Leaks. <https://zenodo.org/records/17009888>
- RangeSanitizer: Detecting Memory Errors with Efficient Range Checks. <https://zenodo.org/records/17009907>

For more information about the project deliverables and publications, visit RESCALE's Zenodo community: [RESCALE Project](#)

Collaboration

RESCALE has initiated a collaboration with the Horizon Europe project **CyberSecDome** to strengthen joint communication and dissemination activities. Following recent discussions with the **CyberSecDome** dissemination team, both projects expressed strong interest in combining forces to maximize outreach and visibility. Planned actions include shared communication campaigns, as well as the organization of an open webinar with sister projects to explore synergies and foster cross-project collaboration.

Events

RESCALE participated in the following events in the 2nd year:

- [Global IoT Day Live Webinar and Roundtable 2025](#)
- [CRA Horizontal Standards Deep Dive Workshop 2025](#)
- [Bright Minds AI Summer Camp 2025](#)
- [Cybersecurity Hands-On Training \(CyberHOT\) Summer School 2025](#)

RESCALE co-organized the:

- [5th International Workshop on Advances on Privacy Preserving Technologies and Solutions \(IWAPS\)](#)

BRIGHT MINDS
AI SUMMER CAMP

ARES

IWAPS

4th International Workshop on Advances on Privacy Preserving Technologies and Solutions

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No **101120962**.

